

Research article (Featured theme: Geolinguistic approaches to linguistic patterns in Asia and Africa)

Numeral systems in Asia and Africa: A geolinguistic approach to linguistic patterns

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Abstract: This article presents new maps of the numeral systems in Asia and Africa and provides interpretations, based on articles in the numeral systems of individual language groups/areas and Fukazawa's (2023a) overview in Chapter XVI of *Linguistic atlas of Asia and Africa III*. These new maps offer new interpretations and possibilities regarding the historical changes between quinary, decimal, vigesimal and other systems.*

Keywords: *Linguistic atlas of Asia and Africa*; numeral systems; counting; numbers

1. Introduction

The purpose of this study is to apply a geolinguistic approach to numeral systems in Asia and Africa. Numeral systems are mainly described as quinary, decimal, vigesimal, and other systems, as shown in Table 1. Yasugi (1990, 1995) describes numeral systems based on the principles of the combination of units and bases in a number sequence. When the powers of a base number are multiples of ten, the numeral system is called the decimal system. In the decimal system, the unit numbers range numbers from 1 to 9, and the base numbers are the ranks, such as 10 (B^1), 100 (B^2), and 1000 (B^3); the unit numbers are added or multiplied by the base numbers.

Fukazawa (2023a) presented a simplified map of the distribution of numeral systems in Asia and Africa. In this paper, new maps were drawn where numeral systems that correspond with the Asian and African geographical points can be seen. The numeral systems' linguistic data and original maps in Asia and Africa were produced by the language group and area experts and were already published in *Linguistic Atlas of Asia and Africa III* (Fukushima et al. eds. 2023). To prepare integrating individual maps, Fukazawa (2023a) assigned a symbol to each system and recommended that experts consider dividing numerals into three major categories, namely, 1 to 10, 10 to 20, and

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even 20 or more (cf. Yasugi 1990, 1995), since each category may have a different system within a language. When a dialect or language has multiple systems, then the symbols are represented with a superimposed notation (Table 1). After the following section, these symbols and the original Asian and African maps will be used.

Table 1 Symbols of numeral systems

Symbol	Numeral system (Counting method)
/	Binary type
	Quinary type
—	Decimal type
○	Vigesimal type
●	Other types, including quaternary and other base number types
<i>N</i>	None type
	Lack of data

Table 2 Language groups and colors

Color	Language group	
	Red	Ainu; Sinitic; Dravidian
	Green	Japonic; Austroasiatic; Mongolic; Nilo-Saharan
	Light blue	Korean; Uralic; Turkic; Caucasian; Kx'a
	Navy blue	Kra-Dai; Indo-Aryan and Nuristani
	Orange	Hmong-Mien; Austronesian; Tungusic; Iranian; Tuu
	Brown	Tibeto-Burman; Semitic; Khoe-Kwadi
	Black	Chukotko-Kamchatkan; Brushaski, Andamanese and language isolates in South Asia

2. Methods and results

The original numeral system maps of each language group or area have been created using the ArcGIS Online, Esri's web-based mapping software, as shown in Fukushima et al. eds. (2023). Figure 1 shows a new map of numeral systems in Asia and Africa in which the original maps were superimposed on each other, using the ArcGIS Online. Figures 2 and 3 show the enlarged maps of the eastern and western parts of Figure 1, respectively. As can be seen from these maps, the decimal system is widely used in Asia and Africa and has been adopted by many language groups and areas, most likely in the process of modernization. Some language groups have a monotonous distribution with the decimal system, such as Japonic, Korean, Sinitic, Hmong-Mien, Kra-Dai, Tungusic, Uralic, and Semitic. The decimal system must also be found in other areas with no numeral data. Here, it is important to note that few areas use more than three systems simultaneously. This may be due to historical changes in the numeral system. Section 3 will focus on regions that have numeral systems other than a decimal system.

Fig. 1 Numeral systems in Asia and Africa

Fig. 2 Numeral systems in Asia and Africa (Eastern)

Fig. 3 Numeral systems in Asia and Africa (Western)

3. Discussion

In Figure 4, the decimal symbol, which is widespread throughout Asia and Africa, is removed from the map of Figure 1. Figures 5 and 6 show enlarged maps of the southern and northern parts of Figure 4, respectively. As for the vigesimal system, it is likely that more languages currently use or have used it around the Pacific coast or in the

southern part of Asia and Africa, although the data for expressing numbers larger than 20 are often lacking (see also Fukazawa 2023a). Typical vigesimal languages often use quinary and/or decimal system(s) for counting up to 20. As mentioned in Section 2, fewer areas use more than three systems simultaneously. It is most likely that, in most cases, the more widespread the decimal system has become, the more quinary and vigesimal systems have been eliminated or (partially) replaced by the decimal system.

Fig. 4 Numeral systems other than the decimal system in Asia and Africa

Fig. 5 Numeral systems other than the decimal system in Asia and Africa (Southern)

Fig. 6 Numeral systems other than the decimal system in Asia and Africa (Northern)

In language groups and areas where both the vigesimal and quinary systems exist, e.g., Papuan, Chukotko-Kamchatkan, and languages around the White Nile area, the geographical points with the quinary system are more widely distributed than those with the vigesimal system. In these regions, it is possible that the vigesimal system emerged and developed after the quinary system areas. Since these regions are on the periphery of Asia and Africa, and were less affected by the expansion of the decimal system, the vigesimal and quinary systems may actually be older than the decimal system, or the decimal system may be older than the quinary and vigesimal systems. The Proto-Austronesian language is known to use a decimal system in the study of the language reconstruction, and as a result of language contact with Papuan languages, languages on the New Guinea mainland, in New Caledonia, and Vanuatu received the quinary and vigesimal systems (Matsumoto 2006 and Utsumi 2023).

The etymons of the base numbers of 5, 10, 20 are often derived from the common concept of counting five fingers and toes, and the combined uses of the quinary/decimal/vigesimal systems are not only historical contacts, but perhaps also occur in sporadic or remote places coincidentally. The etymon of 5 is ‘hand,’ that of 10 is ‘hands,’ and the etymon of 20 is ‘man,’ namely meaning ‘hands and feet.’ (Ono 2023; see also Matsumoto 2006, Nakao 2023 and Utsumi 2023). Menninger (2011 [1969]), suggests “In pure counting natural divisions of 5, 10 and 20—‘hand, hands, man’—are predominant. The physical representation of this process leads to the earliest numerals used by primitive peoples, which we thus designate as *row-characters*.” Fukazawa (2023a, 2023b) mentioned that even in current non-quinary regions, a quinary system is sometimes retained as the etymological fragment of ‘hand’ for the number ‘5,’ and it can be assumed that the quinary system may have been used, such as *asikne* ‘5’ (*asik* < *aske* ‘hand’; *ne* is a copula verb) in the Ainu language.

Binary, quaternary, and other systems, including the no numeral system (None type), appear to be older than the quinary, decimal, and vigesimal systems. In the case where numbers only go up to 3, the language or dialect can be categorized as a None type and would be considered the primitive type before the establishment of the other numeral systems (Matsumoto 2006). The None type examples can be seen in Beá and Jeru in South Asia (Yoshioka 2023), and Tuu, Kx’a and Khoe-Kwadi in the Kalahari Basin Area (Kimura and Nakagawa 2023).

4. Conclusion

In Fukazawa's previous analysis (2023a), the historical changes and transitions of the quinary, decimal, and vigesimal systems were difficult to analyze. However, the new maps of this study provide ways to consider them. Significantly, in the regions where the combined systems of quinary, decimal, and vigesimal systems exist, the etymons of the base numbers 5, 10, and 20 tend to be 'hand,' 'hands,' and 'man.' If the original numeral systems in a language with these base numbers were replaced by the decimal systems of another language, the original systems and forms would be strongly inherited and partially preserved in the language.

Notes for copyrights

The members of the 2020–2023 project involved in the investigation of the numeral systems are the following linguists: ONO Chikako (Chukotko-Kamchatkan), FUKAZAWA Mika (Ainu), Nakazawa Kohei (Japonic), FUKUI Rei (Korean), SUZUKI Fumiaki (Sinitic), TANG Baiyan and TAGUCHI Yoshihisa (Hmong-Mien), TOMITA Aika (Kra-Dai), SHIRAI Satoko, KURABE Keita, EBIHARA Shiho, IWASA Kazue, and SUZUKI Hiroyuki (Tibeto-Burman), MINEGISHI Makoto and SHIMIZU Masaaki (Austroasiatic), UTSUMI Atsuko (Austronesian), MATSUMOTO Ryo (Tungusic and Uralic), SAITÔ Yoshio (Mongolic and Turkic), YOSHIOKA Noboru (South Asia), KODAMA Nozomi (Dravidian), IWASAKI Takamasa (Iranian), SUZUKI Hiroyuki (Caucasian), NAGATO Youichi (Semitic), NAKAO Shuichiro (Nilo-Saharan), and KIMURA Kimihiko and NAKAGAWA Hiroshi (Kalahari Basin Area).

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